

TRANSPORT, LOGISTICS AND TOURISM - A VITAL RELATIONSHIP. POINTS OF REFLECTIONS

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Abstract

Global logistics networks serve as a circulatory system for the corresponding global value-adding chain, in which different components of the logistics network perform different functions in an organisationally unified manner, especially in the tourism activity. Therefore, in order to establish a region as a key component in global logistics networks, it is necessary to develop a vision on how to strategically position the region in the context of the overall global logistics networks. In order to achieve this goal, governments, both individually and collectively, will need to develop and implement systematic policies to deliver the vision. The essence of the global logistics competence also applies to the tourism sector.

Key words: *logistics in tourism, sustainable development, organizational function, public sector.*

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There can be no tourism if there is no movement: a traveler is, by definition, a person who moves, moves from one place to another; therefore, mobility is an essential condition for tourism not only to prosper, but to exist.

The existence of mobility is therefore essential for the very survival of tourism because being a tourist means moving towards a new destination either by choice or suggestion, leaving the place where you reside to leave and reach a new destination. But that doesn't mean that mobility doesn't have some downsides, its shadows that need to be fought and resolved.

Having ascertained that tourist mobility is part of the very soul of tourism, it remains to be understood how to aim for "cleaner" mobility: for tourist mobility to be sustainable, in fact, there are several factors to take into consideration and it is necessary to work on various elements to ensure that the negative aspects do not prevail over the positives in mobility.

Social factors: how is tourist mobility experienced by travelers and the inhabitants of the host places?

Many tourist destinations are increasingly easily accessible thanks to the development of means of transport: but what impact does all this have on tourists and residents of tourist resorts?

The fact that tourist mobility has been made easier by the evolution of transport has allowed many travelers to get to know and visit many more destinations, it is true: but what is the line between a more accessible tourism, between expanding the possibility of travel to more people and the creation of mass tourism that risks leading to the exploitation of areas that were previously better preserved, also thanks to their inaccessibility?

Giving value to experiential tourism and slow tourism starting from a careful choice of means of transport in one's journey can mean not only giving a new imprint to one's holiday, but also reducing the negative impacts that out-of-control tourism can have on inhabitants of a territory.

Economic factors: Tourism can give a strong boost to employment in the transport sector.

When a locality is enhanced from a tourist point of view, its entire economy can benefit from it because there are various sectors that can be more or less directly connected to the tourism sector.

If a place is successful in the tourism field, for example, the revenues of the transport sector experience a moment of surge. Enhancing the tourist potential of a place therefore means stimulating mobility towards this place and within the various areas of this territory. And this has positive economic repercussions because the more active a sector, in this case that of transport, is, the more workforce is needed and the more workforce is needed the more new recruits are hired.

Environmental factors:

Promote sustainable mobility to promote respect for the environment.

Attention to the environment and to problems related to pollution is, fortunately, becoming increasingly popular: the tourism sector cannot fail to take into account the growing importance given to sustainability.

Mobility, so necessary for tourism, also involves a certain energy expenditure and can have a significant negative impact on nature, to push for more sustainable mobility means working in favor of the environment. Transport linked to tourism can and must reduce the pollution produced as much as possible; this is possible by focusing above all on the valorisation of public transport and "alternative means". Traveling means having a starting point, a point from which to decide to move for a period and from this point to move away without ever forgetting to pack a dose of curiosity and more. Curiosity is what pushes the tourist to go outside the usual circuits to discover the truest essence of a place, but in the luggage it is also necessary not to forget to put "respect" between a pair of trousers and the most comfortable shoes in all its forms. Respect also means ECOTOURISM necessary to experience moving from one place to another in a sustainable way. This is the Mission on which to focus to enjoy a holiday without many problems, surprises and worries. And, since we are talking about "eco-tourism", respect for the environment must above all be kept in mind. A healthy environment is the future not only for tourism, but for life itself. Because when you travel you set off to reach a destination in which to live an experience, but the journey itself is also an experience: if tourism is to be sustainable, the means of transport chosen must also be sustainable.

Because respect for the environment cannot be something to be pulled out only when necessary but must be a conscious choice step by step. In fact, the interest in ecology should concern something that invests every area of our life and not an abstract concept to leave at home to travel lighter. Tourism is all the more sustainable the more it is inspired by respect, the c.d. Responsible Tourism. In fact, the word "respect" indicates a whole world made up of attention for the environment we are visiting and made up of the desire to discover a culture while trying in every way not to harm it in the slightest.

When we set off on a journey, especially if in addition to being "tourist-consumers" we choose to be travelers who would like to return home with some intangible but immensely valuable souvenir, we already know how we should behave both towards the environment that surrounds us and towards people around us. Just to continue on the issue of "responsible tourism". Traveling has always been synonymous with curiosity, the desire to see, to know, to understand. In recent years, attention to so-called responsible tourism has grown significantly. The international debate on the theme of sustainable tourism development has grown significantly thanks also, if not above all, to the increasingly significant growth of forms of responsible tourism demand. The concept of "responsible tourism" is made up of a set of good practices and solidarity attitudes, or rather a "new" way of conceiving holidays. Given the complexity of the concept, there is still no objectively recognized definition, but different expressions (sustainable tourism, supportive, fair, ecotourism, etc.).

So, a way of travelling, which obviously also affects the transport system, which pushes people to make their own choices by embracing the values of sobriety and respect for the local environmental,

social, economic and cultural context. Among other things, the responsible tourist is therefore the one who travels in search of the possibility of living authentic tourist experiences in close contact with the local community and driven by the desire to promote/support the well-being of the local host community (for example, favoring the purchase of local products).

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